

STATE SUPPORT OF DOMESTIC TOURISM IN THE CONTEXT OF THE COVID-19 CONSEQUENCES AND FINANCIAL CONSTRAINTS

Ekaterina Baranova*, Rita Stytsyuk**, Sergey Makushkin***, Aleksandr Shelygov****, Tatiana Ukhina***** & Diana Stepanova*****

Abstract

Tourism is a sector that constitutes a significant part of many economies. Over the years, the tourism sector has proven its resilience and ability not only to recover from economic crises but also to contribute to economic and social recovery. The article aims at proposing practical measures for the state support of tourism activities in Russia in the context of the COVID-19 consequences and financial constraints on business. The study considers the measures taken in different countries to promote the development of domestic tourism in a pandemic. Based on an expert survey, state support measures for the development of domestic tourism are proposed as the most sustainable socio-economic model of tourism in the context of the post-COVID restrictions and imposed sanctions. It has been concluded that the reorientation and development of domestic tourism is, among other things, a type of adaptation that is necessary for Russian tourism and the economy to overcome the coronavirus consequences and the financial constraints of business.

Keywords: Domestic tourism; State regulation; State support; Budget financing; Brand management; Public-private partnership.

APOIO ESTATAL AO TURISMO INTERNO NO CONTEXTO DAS CONSEQUÊNCIAS E RESTRIÇÕES FINANCEIRAS DA COVID-19

Resumo

O turismo é um setor que constitui uma parte significativa de muitas economias. Ao longo dos anos, este setor tem demonstrado a sua resiliência e capacidade não só de recuperar de crises econômicas, mas também de contribuir para a recuperação econômica e social. O artigo visa propor medidas práticas para o apoio estatal às atividades turísticas na Rússia, no contexto das consequências da COVID-19 e dos constrangimentos financeiros às empresas. O estudo considera as medidas tomadas em diferentes países para promover o desenvolvimento do turismo interno numa pandemia. Com base em um levantamento bibliográfico e empírico, com experts, são propostas medidas de apoio estatal para o desenvolvimento do turismo doméstico como o modelo socioeconômico mais sustentável de turismo no contexto das restrições pós-COVID e das sanções impostas. Concluiu-se que a reorientação e desenvolvimento do turismo doméstico é, entre outras coisas, um tipo de adaptação necessária para que o turismo russo e a economia para superar as consequências do coronavírus e as restrições financeiras das empresas.

Palavras-chave: Turismo doméstico; Regulamentação do Estado; Apoio do Estado; Financiamento do orçamento; Gestão de marcas; Parceria público-privada.

APOYO ESTATAL AL TURISMO INTERNO EN EL CONTEXTO DE LAS CONSECUENCIAS DE LA COVID-19 Y LAS LIMITACIONES FINANCIERAS

Resumen

El turismo es un sector que constituye una parte importante de muchas economías. A lo largo de los años, el sector turístico ha demostrado su resistencia y capacidad no sólo para recuperarse de las crisis económicas, sino también para contribuir a la recuperación económica y social. El artículo tiene por objeto proponer medidas prácticas para el apoyo estatal a las actividades turísticas en Rusia en el contexto de las consecuencias de la COVID-19 y las limitaciones financieras de las empresas. El estudio considera las medidas adoptadas en diferentes países para promover el desarrollo del turismo interno en una pandemia. Basándose en una encuesta de expertos, se proponen medidas de apoyo estatal para el desarrollo del turismo interno como el modelo socioeconómico más sostenible del turismo en el contexto de las restricciones y sanciones impuestas tras el COVID. Se ha llegado a la conclusión de que la reorientación y el desarrollo del turismo interno es, entre otras cosas, un tipo de adaptación necesaria para que el turismo y la economía rusos superen las consecuencias del coronavirus y las limitaciones financieras de las empresas.

Palabras clave: Turismo doméstico; Regulación estatal; Apoyo del Estado; Financiación presupuestaria; Gestión de la marca; Colaboración público-privada.

1 INTRODUCTION

Tourism has long been an important component within the infrastructure of many countries, influencing their development indirectly or even directly (Higgins-Desbiolles, Camicelli, Krolikowski, Wijesinghe, & Boluk, 2019). A well-developed infrastructure, the provision of high-quality services, favorable climatic conditions, and historical, cultural, and architectural achievements increase the

profitability of the tourism industry (Skanavis & Sakellari, 2011). Tourism can be regarded as one of the tools for the effective and dynamic development of the economy.

In recent years, the tourism industry has been one of the fastest growing industries, sometimes surpassing the global economy as a whole. However, the COVID-19 spread and quarantine restrictions have drastically changed all socio-ecological and economic ties (Chebli & Ben Said, 2020).

Licenciada por Creative Commons
4.0 / Internacional CC BY 4.0

* Candidate of Pedagogic Sciences; Associate Professor; K.G. Razumovsky Moscow State University of Technologies and Management (First Cossack University), Moscow, Russia. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5409-9873> [ea.baranova@mquim.ru]

** Doctor of Economic Sciences; Professor; Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation, Moscow, Russia. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1906-3645> [rita.yu.stytsyuk@mail.ru]

*** Candidate of History Sciences, Professor; Russian State Social University, Moscow, Russia. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8427-3991> [S_makin2009@mail.ru]

**** Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor; Moscow Polytechnic University, Moscow, Russia. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1082-628X> [shelygov@mail.ru]

***** Candidate of Economic Sciences; Russian State University of Tourism and Service, Moscow, Russia. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6690-2451> [3332221@mail.ru]

***** Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor; Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Moscow, Russia. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5981-6889> [s_diana@mail.ru]

This context imposes some challenges to the countries, societies, firms and people. At the national level, the first challenge hindering the development of external tourism in Russia is the COVID-19 consequences. The second challenge is the financial constraints faced by Russian tourism at the present time (Averin, Pozdnyakov, & Svagdiene, 2021). The combination of the above-mentioned issues stipulates the need to develop domestic tourism more and more required by the Russian population.

Under the conditions of financial constraints, the transformation of tourism demand also creates opportunities for the development of domestic tourism in Russia and its state support, whose study is a relevant area of scientific research. Thus, this research aims to review and analyze the international proposed measures of state support for the development of domestic tourism (public-private partnership, brand management, budget financing) in the context of the pandemic consequences and financial constraints on businesses. This kind of study can be useful to identify best practices and generate references and models of action, helping the faster recovery from pandemics.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Many economic studies emphasize (Schmidt & Woll, 2014; Stahl, 2019) that the instruments of state support should mitigate an unfavorable economic situation, therefore the state plays an important role in the organization and functioning of the economic system. This role comes down to a compromise between ensuring the best conditions for the functioning of the market (for example, the tourism services market) and the need to eliminate the negative consequences associated with a crisis (Zohlnhöfer, Engler, & Dümig, 2018), in particular the COVID-19 spread and financial constraints on business (Farzanegan, Gholipour, Feizi, Nunkoo, & Andargoli, 2020).

There is a debate among economists regarding the real effects of different forms of state support. According to Berry (2021), it is widely believed that large-scale interventions in the economy are not only consistent with neoliberalism but might even be one of its defining features.

In relation to the tourism sector, scientific literature considers state support in different ways. Kuklina (2017) claims that state support considers various impacts of the external environment and, on their basis, forms strategic directions for the implementation of public administration functions.

Demchenko and Kabirov (2013) believe that state support in the tourism industry is a set of techniques and methods of purposeful influence exercised by state authorities on the activities of economic entities and market conditions in order to ensure the best conditions for the functioning of the market mechanism, the implementation of state socio-economic priorities and the creation of a unified concept of development.

Scholars divide the forms and methods of state support of tourism activities into three groups: support for tourism demand, support for tourism supply, and general support measures (Amosov & Ashinova, 2021; Desyatnichenko & Kuklina, 2016; Kuklina & Desyatnichenko, 2017). State support measures for tourism demand are as follows: state

marketing and promotion of the country's tourism brand, state influence on pricing, facilitating access to tourist facilities, as well as the development and support of social tourism (Amosov & Ashinova, 2021). State support measures for tourism supply comprise the research and planning of tourism activities and the creation of favorable conditions for investment in tourism (Desyatnichenko & Kuklina, 2016). General measures of state support in tourism include grants for the development of certain types of tourism, soft loans from government bodies; the sale and lease of land plots at a price that is significantly lower than the market price, preferential tax treatment for investors, as well as subsidies for the development of transport and communications (Kuklina & Desyatnichenko, 2017).

The analysis of the relevant literature allows reviewing the support measures that are used in some countries of the world to stabilize the tourism industry and identifying the best practices supporting tourism during a pandemic:

1. *Financial assistance to economic entities* (subsidies, grants, and interest-free loans to maintain their liquidity). For example, travel companies in South Korea can receive preferential unsecured financing at a reduced interest rate (1%) (Gössling, Scott, & Hall, 2020).

2. *Wage subsidies*. For example, the British government used a variety of measures to support travel companies in order to retain staff working with clients and establish ties among travel companies. Almost 1.5 million euros were allocated to fund organizations involved in the marketing of tourist destinations. The tourism business can ask the government to cover the costs of maintaining no more than two employees with a monthly salary of up to 2,800 euros, as well as the employer's insurance and pension contributions for three months (Baum & Hai, 2020).

3. *Tax holidays, tax deferrals, and benefits*. For instance, travel companies in Germany were allowed to defer tax payments until the end of 2020 (Sigala, 2020).

4. *No contributions to Social Security from salary earnings*. In the United States, Social Security tax payments for employers and the self-employed had been deferred until January 1, 2021 (Bakar & Rosbi, 2020).

5. *Communication and marketing campaigns for the formation of deferred demand and the promotion of tourist attractions*. For example, the government in South Korea issues discount coupons that can be used to offset tourism expenses (Khazami, Lakner, & Nefzi, 2020).

We cannot but agree with scholars (Demchenko & Kabirov, 2013; Larionova, Chernikova, & Fedlyuk, 2019; Lonshakova, 2010) who consider public-private partnerships (Demchenko & Kabirov, 2013), brand management (Lonshakova, 2010), and budget financing (Larionova et al., 2019) to be the main methods of state support for domestic tourism.

The corresponding literature interprets public-private partnerships in the tourism sector as a system of legally formalized relations between public authorities that regulate the processes of organizing recreation at the micro, meso, and macro levels, as well as state recreational and tourism institutions. The latter help to create or improve infrastructure, goods, services, or resources through the implementation of certain projects (Demchenko & Kabirov, 2013).

Today there are more than 100 public-private

partnerships in the sphere of tourism. These projects are implemented in a wide range of countries, with different levels of economic development and tourism potential (Markova, Listopad, Shelygov, Fedorov, & Kiselevich, 2021). Some projects are focused on the development of tourism in the country as a whole (Thailand, Australia, Nepal, the Caribbean, Canada, Ghana); other projects strive to promote certain destinations and/or certain types of tourism (Cyprus, national parks, etc.). There are also projects related to the development of a certain tourist attraction (Armada Hotel in Istanbul, Disneyland Park in Paris) (Bakar & Rosbi, 2020).

While analyzing brand management as a measure to support domestic tourism, it should be noted that branding is an effective tool to determine not only the uniqueness of a tourist destination but also to develop the investment attractiveness of a particular region (Lonshakova, 2010).

Important components for developing domestic tourism are financial support and budget financing, whose sources are state, regional and local budgets.

According to scholars (Larionova et al., 2019), a delay in providing adequate financial support to the tourism industry can not only weaken competitive positions but also lead to the loss of the existing cultural heritage, whose restoration will require even greater financial costs.

Thus, ensuring proper budget financing of the tourism industry in order to improve the functioning of domestic tourism is one of the priorities of the economy. At the same time, a prerequisite for the effective functioning of domestic tourism is the optimal combination of budget financing tools, the rational use of all types of resources in financial and economic activities, and the social responsibility of the tourism business (Bochkareva, Solovyeva, Farikova, & Khamidullin, 2022).

Given the importance of domestic tourism and current trends, a large number of countries are taking steps to grow their domestic markets. The countries of Latin America attracting domestic tourists are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The measures taken around the world to promote the development of domestic tourism during a pandemic.

Measure to develop domestic tourism	Country	Examples of developing domestic tourism
Public-private partnership	Ecuador	The development and implementation of training programs on various topics that are interesting to tourists in order to improve the skills and knowledge of human resources associated with the tourism sector
	Bolivia	The modernization of airport terminals throughout the country, including El Dorado International Airport
	Germany	Collaborative initiatives between the government and private sector to improve tourist attractions and infrastructure
Brand management	Argentina	The creation of the Domestic Tourism Observatory to identify the best travel destinations for Argentinian tourist
	Brazil	The promotion of tourist destinations to encourage and motivate potential tourists based on various planned activities: a) participation in fairs; b) press trips; c) promotional trips; d) material design
Budget financing	Australia	Branding campaigns to highlight unique experiences and attractions in different regions of the country
	Chile	Financial assistance packages for SMEs in the tourism sector, including tax deferrals, tax flexibility and other ways to provide more liquidity to affected enterprises
	Argentina	Emergency budget funds and programs to help companies and employees in such hardest-hit sectors as tourism
	Italy	Direct funding and grants to support the recovery and development of tourism, including investment in infrastructure and promotion

Source: Compiled based on (Bayih & Singh, 2020; Sigala, 2020; State aid..., 2022; Akbar, Sharp, 2023).

Despite different classifications, every country tries to support the tourism sector by introducing certain measures. In the context of the COVID-19 consequences and financial constraints on business, we have dwelled on this issue (Kozhamzharova et al., 2022).

This study aims at developing effective measures of state support for domestic tourism used by government bodies and business entities. In this connection, the study should consider possible measures of state support for domestic tourism in the context of the COVID-19 consequences and financial constraints on business.

3 METHODS

To solve the tasks set, we used general scientific methods: (a) theoretical: the analysis of scientific sources on the research problem; and (b) empirical: an expert survey. The study was conducted in three stages between February and April 2022. At the first stage, we studied scientific and analytical works on the research topic. The analysis of the

corresponding publications allows determining the essence of state support for the tourism industry (Amoako et al., 2022), world practices in supporting tourism during a pandemic (Gössling et al., 2020), as well as measures taken to stimulate the development of domestic tourism (Arbulú et al., 2021).

At the second stage, we had online communication with the experts (Šaparnienė et al., 2022). The expert survey was carried out in Russian via e-mail. All the respondents were informed about the objective of the survey and our intention to publish its results in a generalized form.

We sent e-mails to 55 experts and asked them the following question: "What are the necessary measures of state support for the development of domestic tourism at the present stage?". The respondents included managers and employees of travel companies, professors from the Russian State Social University, Moscow Polytechnic University, Russian State University of Tourism and Service, and Plekhanov Russian University of Economics in the disciplines "Tourism" and related areas. The experts were asked to substantiate their answers in a free form. Fifty-two

experts filled out the form and three experts refused to participate in the survey.

After receiving the answers, the experts were asked, depending on the significance of the measures of state support, to arrange them on a scale of order and assign points. The rank of each measure of state support was determined, according to the points attributed by the experts.

For a more objective analysis of the data obtained during the expert survey, the compliance of expert opinions was mathematically measured using Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W) (Deng et al., 2022):

$$W = 12S/n^2(m^3-m),$$

where S is the sum of the squared deviations of all ranks given to each state support measure from the average value; n is the number of experts; m is the number of state support measures.

Further, the information obtained during the expert survey was processed to determine the impacts of state support measures, form a rank transformation matrix, and calculate the arithmetic mean of impacts for each of the state support measures. The final impacts identify the significance of state support measures from the viewpoint of experts.

4 RESULTS

4.1 The Research Content

Travelling abroad is declining amid restrictions caused by the COVID-19 spread, financial restrictions on businesses, and a significant increase in the cost of leisure. According to the Federal State Statistics Service (2022), prices for Turkish resorts, popular with Russians tourists, soared by 92% in April 2022 compared to the same period last year (Ukhina, Maidanevych, Abdimomynova, Stepanova, & Zambinova, 2021). At the same time, the average cost of a tour to Turkey increased from 30,500 rubles in April 2021 to 58,800 rubles in 2022. According to statistics from the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of Turkey, Russian tourists made 130,150 trips to Turkey in April 2022, which is 16.6% less than in 2021.

In 2021, domestic tourist flows amounted to 56.5 million people if compared to the planned value of 52.2 million. The government forecasts 61.2 million domestic tourists by the end of 2022. The state has allocated 70 billion rubles to support tourism, create infrastructure and increase the availability of recreation for Russians in 2022 if compared to 45.9 billion rubles in 2021 and only 7 billion rubles in 2019.

In 2020, a tourist cashback program was launched (the refund of some costs for participants in the tourism development program) that became the most popular support measure in the industry. In 2021, more than 1.7 million people used it. In 2022, 2.4 million tourists received cashback when buying vouchers. About 8.4 billion rubles have been returned to the MIR tourist cards as compensation.

The launch of the children's cashback program in 2021 was equally important, which allows parents to return 50% of a ticket cost to a summer camp. Thanks to this program, more than 400,000 children spent their summer in camps throughout Russia in 2021.

Thus, it is necessary to continue the development of domestic tourism. In this connection, the "Tourism and Hospitality Industry" national project was launched in Russia in 2021, aimed at developing domestic tourism through budget financing and public-private partnerships. It is planned to allocate 529 billion rubles from the federal budget and 72 billion rubles from regional funds for the project implementation until 2030. In addition, the national project should attract a large number of private investments (about 2 trillion rubles), with some of them being directed to the creation of a modern tourist infrastructure (Iudina et al., 2021).

The project plans to increase the tourist flow in Russia to 140 million trips by 2030, as well as to create twice as many jobs in the industry, implement about 600 infrastructure projects, build new tourist facilities and form tourist macro-territories throughout the country. At the end of 2021, 27 public-private partnerships were implemented in the tourism sector with a total investment of 5 billion rubles.

However, the development of domestic tourism has faced some challenges. Firstly, many regions still had severe COVID-19 restrictions that did not contribute to the development of tourism, which were lifted only at the beginning of 2022. Secondly, most regions of Russia are characterized by low purchasing power. Although the real disposable income of the population in 2021, according to official data, increased by 3.1%, this figure was achieved in part due to one-time social payments (to pensioners and parents with children under 18).

In absolute terms, the monetary income of Russians, according to the Federal State Statistics Service, is on average 39,854 rubles per capita per month (approximately US\$ 468,68 dollars), for which it is difficult to make several trips per year (Reznikova, Ganieva, Verna, Korolenko, & Shelygov, 2020). For example, the calculation of vacation pay in Russia is based on the average earnings for the year, including salary, bonuses, allowances, etc. The total income for the last 12 months is divided by the number of days worked, applying a coefficient of 29.3 (the average number of calendar days in a month, excluding holidays) (Vacation pay calculation in 2023, 2022).

With a budget of approximately 40,000 rubles per month and a standard vacation of 28 days per year, a person could plan a 10-day getaway for example, to St. Petersburg. With an estimated daily expenditure of 3,000 to 4,000 rubles, they can allocate funds for accommodation (around 1,500 to 3,000 rubles per night), meals (1,000 to 1,500 rubles per day), local transportation (200 to 300 rubles per day), and activities/entrance fees (500 to 1,000 rubles per day). [Note: 1 US\$ = 90 rubles, in July 26, 2023].

4.2 The Results of an Expert Survey

The analysis of scientific literature has shown that under the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic and, in particular, the financial constraints of business, reorientation to the development of domestic tourism is one of the directions for improving domestic tourism. In the course of an expert survey, the respondents proposed the following measures of state support for the development of domestic tourism in the context of the COVID-19 consequences and financial constraints on businesses (Table 2).

Table 2. The measures of state support for developing domestic tourism.

No.	Measures	Content	%*	Ranking	Impact
1	Public-private partnership	Building an effective model of public-private partnerships in the tourism sphere with the involvement of leading businesses, local communities, government bodies, scientific communities, etc.	84.6%	1	0.45
2	Brand management	Creating a network of regional tourism brands as identifiers of some territory promotion and active state support for brand messages ("Travel around Russia!")	78.8%	2	0.31
3	Budget financing	The budgetary financing of the Russian tourism industry through the implementation of national and local programs for the development of domestic tourism	73.1%	3	0.24

Note: * – % of expert references.

Source: own elaboration.

According to the calculations based on the expert survey, the concordance coefficient was $W = 0.79$ ($p < 0.01$), which indicates a strong consistency of expert opinions.

Thus, the experts consider the creation of an effective public-private partnership with the involvement of large-, medium- and small-sized tourism enterprises, volunteers, government bodies, and scientific communities as the main measures of state support for the development of domestic tourism. The formation of a network of regional tourism brands as part of territory promotion is also an important measure for the development of domestic tourism.

In addition, the experts suggest introducing the budgetary financing of the Russian tourism industry through the implementation of national ("Tourism and Hospitality Industry" national project) and local programs for the development of domestic.

5 DISCUSSION

While commenting on the measures of state support for the development of domestic tourism, the experts emphasize the need for cooperation between central government bodies and regional and local authorities that regulate tourism activities and private business. Such cooperation is perfect for finding forms of effective cooperation and interaction in order to attract financial resources from the private sector and meet the growing needs of the tourism industry (Kuklina, 2017).

Its consequence is the functioning of mixed institutions in terms of ownership (public and private) in the field of tourism activities. The mechanism of public-private partnerships allows the mixed financing of individual projects in specific sectors of the economy by both state bodies and private investors (Lonshakova, 2010). If compared to other financing mechanisms, a public-private partnership is based on different goals of its parties: the state is interested in increasing the volume and improving the quality of tourism services, while the business aims at increasing its profits (Demchenko & Kabirov, 2013).

5.1 Public-private Partnership

According to the experts (Nikolai K. and Viktor L., heads of travel companies), the creation of public-private partnerships improves tourism activities in the following areas: financial support for transport companies to increase their load; joint programs to promote new directions in tourism; discounts for various types of tourist services;

common groups for the search, collection, and analysis of information on the tourism market; improving the efficiency of tourism facilities management.

The practice of public-private partnerships in the field of tourism has enough examples of cooperation between state and business structures, which can be conditionally divided into three main areas (Kuklina, 2017):

- 1) Cooperation in the field of complex projects related to the need for significant investments in engineering infrastructure and communications (concession agreements, the leasing or direct state financing of infrastructure projects);
- 2) Cooperation in the field of creating objects of tourism and entertainment infrastructure (using various tools to stimulate the private sector: benefits, taxes, loans, etc.);
- 3) Cooperation in the field of marketing and promotion of national tourism products.

The results of public-private partnerships in the field of tourism can be both tangible (the creation of tourist information centers, purchase of new equipment, the formation of an enterprise, theme park, rural estates, temporary premises, tourist trails, etc.) and intangible (the creation of a tourism cluster, tourist recreational zone, destination, destination repositioning, the development of software, the introduction of certain types of tourism, the implementation of a program for the development of tourism enterprises, improving the safety of tourists, program management, etc.).

5.2 Brand Management

Summarizing the expert opinions, we can conclude that a regional tourism brand is a set of impressions about a particular region that are formed in the minds of consumers (investors or tourists) and determine its role in the tourism market, i.e. its rating among other regions. In addition, a regional tourism brand is an important element in ensuring social stability. This is achieved as the brand increases the self-esteem of local residents, making their life more comfortable and less conflict-ridden (Demchenko & Kabirov, 2013). The result of successful branding is a certain image of the region, including its past, present, and future.

According to the expert (Sergey K., manager in a travel company), the main idea of a regional tourism brand is based on the need to create an image of this region as a place for active and healthy recreation with a well-developed infrastructure that can satisfy the most demanding consumers. In addition to quantitative indicators, the result of successful branding is the harmonious perception of the newly created brand by the local residents.

5.3 Budget financing

The budget financing of the Russian tourism industry through the implementation of national and local programs for the development of domestic tourism should comprise the following activities. Firstly, financial sources are special funds of the state budget covering salaries expenses, including deductions, utility bills, and other costs associated with the use and maintenance of travel companies (Amosov & Ashinova, 2021). Secondly, there are tax benefits (personal

income tax compensation) for travelers in Russia and users of spa services (Desyatnichenko & Kuklina, 2016). Thirdly, a zero rate of the unified social tax for small- and medium-sized enterprises operating in the field of tourism and hospitality (Desyatnichenko & Kuklina, 2016). It is also necessary to suspend payments under loan agreements with parties of tourism activities as debtors, restructure payments to private banks and ensure concessional lending for the development of domestic tourism (Kuklina & Desyatnichenko, 2017).

Table 3. Synthesis of Measures for the Development of Domestic Tourism.

Categories	Measures from literature	Measures from data	What they have in common
Brand management	Creating a network of regional tourism brands as identifiers of territory promotion	Creating a network of regional tourism brands as identifiers of territory promotion	The establishment of regional tourism brands to promote specific territories and receive active state support for brand messages.
Public-Private Partnership	Building an effective model of public-private partnerships in the tourism sphere with the involvement of leading businesses, local communities, government bodies, scientific communities, etc.	Building an effective model of public-private partnerships in the tourism sphere with the involvement of large-, medium- and small-sized tourism enterprises, volunteers, government bodies, and scientific communities	The establishment of public-private partnerships in the tourism industry involving various stakeholders, including businesses, local communities, government bodies, and scientific communities, to enhance cooperation, attract financial resources, and meet the industry's needs.
Budget Financing	The budgetary financing of the tourism industry through the implementation of national and local programs for the development of domestic tourism	The budgetary financing of the Russian tourism industry through the implementation of national ("Tourism and Hospitality Industry" national project) and local programs for the development of domestic tourism	The allocation of financial resources from the budget to support the development of the tourism industry through national and local programs, including the "Tourism and Hospitality Industry" national project.

Source: own elaboration.

6 CONCLUSION

In the context of the COVID-19 consequences and problems of transport logistics in Russia, interest in domestic tourism is growing, therefore its development is one of the most promising areas for the recovery of tourism. The study results have revealed the main measures of state support for the development of domestic tourism, namely public-private partnership, brand management, and budget financing.

Public-private partnerships in the tourism sector have positive consequences not only for this industry but also for other activities. Public-private partnerships are based on cooperation between state and business on a mutually beneficial basis. If the state effectively performs its functions and creates a favorable environment for the development of the tourism business, this leads to an increase in the number of jobs, tax revenues to the state budget, and the development of territories.

The effective cooperation between state and business structures has also been confirmed by world practice. The implementation of public-private partnerships can take place throughout the country and concern only a specific territory or a specific tourism product.

Successful tourism branding is also an effective means of influencing public opinion, which helps to understand the diversity of culture and history of a particular region. Another effective measure will be the budgetary financing of the tourism industry through the implementation of national and local programs for the development of domestic tourism.

Further research might study the mechanisms and tools of public-private partnerships and brand management as measures of state support for the development of domestic tourism. The study results can be used in regional programs aimed at the development of domestic tourism.

REFERENCES

- Akbar, S., & Sharp, A. (2023). The growth of aboriginal tourism in remote Australia: Indigenist method for an operator perspective. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2023.2180724>
- Amoako, G.K., Obuobisa-Darko, T., Ohene Marfo, S. (2022). Stakeholder role in tourism sustainability: the case of Kwame Nkrumah Mausoleum and centre for art and culture in Ghana. *International Hospitality Review*, 36(1), 25-44. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IHR-09-2020-0057>
- Amosov, A. S., & Ashinova, M. K. (2021). Mery podderzhki rossiiskogo turizma v usloviyakh pandemii koronavirusa COVID-19 [The measures supporting the Russian tourism during the COVID-19 pandemic]. *Novye Tekhnologii*, 17(5), 65-72.
- Arbulú, I., Razumova, M., Rey-Maqueira, J., & Sastre, F. (2021). Can domestic tourism relieve the COVID-19 tourist industry crisis? The case of Spain. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2021.100568>
- Averin, A. V., Pozdnyakov, K. K., & Svagdiene, B. (2021). O problemakh razvitiya turizma i industrii gostepriimstva v Rossii [On the development of tourism and hospitality in

- Russia]. *Vestnik Altaiskoi Akademii Ekonomiki i Prava*, 12(3), 419-426.
- Bakar, N. A., & Rosbi, S. (2020). Effect of Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) to tourism industry. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science*, 7(4), 189-193.
- Baum, T., & Hai, N. T. T. (2020). Hospitality, tourism, human rights and the impact of COVID-19. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 32(7), 2397-2407.
- Bayih, B. E., & Singh, A. (2020). Modeling domestic tourism: motivations, satisfaction and tourist behavioral intentions. *Heliyon*, 6, e04839. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04839
- Berry, C. (2021). The substitutive state? Neoliberal state interventionism across industrial, housing and private pensions policy in the UK. *Competition & Change*, 26(2), 242-265.
- Bochkareva, E. A., Solovyeva, S. V., Farikova, E. A., & Khamidullin, K. Sh. (2022). Mechanisms of balancing Russian budget system in the conditions of economic turbulence. *Revista Relações Internacionais do Mundo Atual*, 2(35), 322-335.
- Chebli, A., & Ben Said, F. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on tourist consumption behavior: a perspective article. *Journal of Tourism Management Research*, 2, 196-207.
- Demchenko, S. G., & Kabirov, I. S. (2013). Gosudarstvennaya podderzhka sfery turizma [The state support of tourism]. *Izvestiya Sochinskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta*, 3(26), 38-44.
- Deng, W., Wang, J., & Zhang, R. (2022). Measures of concordance and testing of independence in multivariate structure. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmva.2022.105035>
- Desyatnichenko, D. Yu., & Kuklina, E. A. (2016). Upravlenie razvitiem turizma i rekreatsii v regione: Teoreticheskie osnovy i prakticheskie napravleniya deyatelnosti [Managing the development of tourism and recreation in a region: Theoretical foundations and practical directions of activity]. *Upravlencheskoe Konsultirovanie*, 5, 68-74.
- Farzanegan, R. M., Gholipour, H. F., Feizi, M., Nunkoo, R., & Andargoli, E. A. (2020). International tourism and outbreak of Coronavirus (COVID-19): A cross-country analysis. *Journal of Travel Research*, 60(3), 687-692.
- Federal State Statistics Service. (2022). Retrieved from <https://rosstat.gov.ru/>
- Gössling, S., Scott, D., & Hall, C. M. (2020). Pandemics, tourism, and global change: A rapid assessment of COVID-19. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 29(5), 1747-1764. doi: 10.1080/09669582.2020.1758708
- Higgins-Desbiolles, F., Carricelli, S., Krolkowski, C., Wijesinghe, G., & Boluk, K. (2019). De-growing tourism: Rethinking tourism. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 27(12), 1926-1944.
- Iudina, E. V., Suzana, L. B., Maksimov, D. V., Skoromets, E. K., Ponyaeva, T. A., & Ksenofontova, E. A. (2021). Application of information technologies to improve the quality of services provided to the tourism industry under the COVID-19 restrictions. *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, 22(6), 7-12.
- Khazami, N., Lakner, Z., & Nefzi, A. (2020) Pandemic and tourism: Re-preparation of tourism post COVID-19. *The Journal of Business and Hotel Management*, 9(2), 89-95.
- Kozhamzharova, G., Omarbakiyev, L., Kogut, O., Zhumasheva, S., Saulembekova, A., & Abdrakhmanova, G. (2022). Banking risks and lending to tourism and hotel businesses amid the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 13(2), 427-437.
- Kuklina, E. A. (2017). Gosudarstvennaya podderzhka sfery turizma i rekreatsii v Rossii: faktory povysheniya konkurentosposobnosti, riski, perspektivy razvitiya [The state support of tourism and recreation in Russia: factors for increasing competitiveness, risks and development prospects]. *Upravlencheskoe Konsultirovanie*, 8, 43-54.
- Kuklina, E. A., & Desyatnichenko, D. Yu. (2017). O gosudarstvennoi politike v sfere turizma i rekreatsii (v kontekste luchshikh mirovykh praktik) [On state policy in the sphere of tourism and recreation (in the context of the best world practices)]. *Upravlencheskoe Konsultirovanie*, 10, 15-30.
- Larionova, A. A., Chernikova, L. I., & Fedlyuk, E. V. (2019). Strategicheskie priority razvitiya vnutrennego turizma – Sbalansirovanoe razvitiye subektov Rossiiskoi Federatsii korporativnym biznesom [Strategic priorities of developing domestic tourism – The balanced development of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation by corporate business]. *Voprosy Regionalnoi Ekonomiki*, 3(40), 56-68.
- Lonshakova, N. E. (2010). *Publitsnaya politika v sfere turizma: Sovershenstvovanie mekhanizma ee formirovaniya i realizatsii* [Public policy in the tourism industry: Improving the mechanism for its formation and implementation]: Extended abstract of thesis for a Candidate Degree in Political Sciences: 23.00.02. State University of Management, Moscow, Russia, 24 p.
- Markova, O. V., Listopad, E. Y., Shelygov, A. V., Fedorov, A. G., & Kiselevich, I. V. (2021). Economic and legal aspects of the innovative activity of enterprises in the context of the digital economy. *Nexo Revista Cientifica*, 34(2), 964-972.
- Reznikova, O. S., Ganieva, A. K., Verna, V. V., Korolenko, J. N., & Shelygov, A. V. (2020). Determinants of the Russian labor market model. *Revista Inclusiones*, 7, 260-267.
- Schmidt, V. A., & Woll, C. (2014). The state: The bête noire of neoliberalism or its greatest conquest? In V. A. Schmidt, & M. Thatcher (Eds.), *Resilient liberalism in Europe's political economy* (pp. 112-142). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Sigala, M. (2020). Tourism and COVID-19: Impacts and implications for advancing and resetting industry and research. *Journal of Business Research*, 117, 312-321.
- Skanavis, C., & Sakellari, M. (2011). International tourism, domestic tourism and environmental change: Environmental education can find the balance. *Tourismos*, 6(1), 233-249.
- Stahl, R. M. (2019). Economic liberalism and the state: Dismantling the myth of naïve laissez-faire. *New Political Economy*, 24(19), 473-486.
- State aid: *Commission approves €698 million Italian scheme to support the tourism sector in the context of coronavirus pandemic*. (May 11th, 2022). An official website of the European Union. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_2_2803
- Šaparnienė, D., Mejerė, O., Raišutienė, J., Juknevičienė, V., & Rupulevičienė, R. (2022). Expression of Behavior and Attitudes toward Sustainable Tourism in the Youth Population: A Search for Statistical Types. *Sustainability*, 14(1), 473. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su14010473>
- Ukhina, T. V., Maidanovich, Y. P., Abdimomynova, A. S., Stepanova, D. I., & Zambinova, G. K. (2021). Tourism after lockdown: Will business travel maintain popularity? *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 12(8), 2217-2223.
- Vacation pay calculation in 2023. (February 17th, 2022). *Rest in Russia The project of "Komsomolskaya Pravda"*. Retrieved from: <https://www.kp.ru/russia/soveti-turistam/raschet-otpusknykh/>
- Zohlhöfer, R., Engler, F., & Dümig, K. (2018). The retreat of the interventionist state in advanced democracies. *British Journal of Political Science*, 48(2), 535-562.

Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5	A.6
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+	+	+	+	+	+
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+	+	+	+	+	+
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	+	+	+	+	+	+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+	+	+	+	+	+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+	+	+	+	+	+
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+	+	+	+	+	+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+	+	+	+	+	+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+	+	+	+	+	+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages	+	+	+	+	+	+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+	+	+	+	+	+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	+	+	+	+	+	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+	+	+	+	+	+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

Processo Editorial / Editorial Process / Proceso Editorial
 Editor Chefe / Editor-in-chief / Editor Jefe: PhD Thiago D. Pimentel (UFJF).
 Recebido / Received / Recibido: 31.10.2022; Revisado / Revised / Revisado: 04.12.2023 – 15.02.2023 – 23.05.2023; Aprobado / Approved /
 Aprobado: 30.06.2023; Publicado / Published / Publicado: 28.07.2023.
 Seção revisada às cegas por pares / Double-blind peer review section / Sesión revisada por pares ciegos.